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Historical Sciences

THE VALUE OF PATRIOTIC EDUCATION OF YOUTH IN RUSSIA

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Abstract

The article discusses the factors for increasing the effectiveness of the patriotic education of young people, the search for funds and technologies that are commensurate with this process in Russia. It is shown that the task of patriotic education today is to form an enlightened and convinced patriot-citizen who has not only a sense of love for the Motherland, but also knowledge of its history, culture, and involvement in the life of the people. Particular attention is paid to the revival of lost rites and holidays, which can be an effective way to introduce modern youth to their cultural roots based on patriotic beliefs and feelings, awareness of the inextricable connection with their people, their traditional way of life.

Keywords: church, patriotism, people, state, faith.

I. INTRODUCTION

The content and direction of patriotism are determined, first of all, by the spiritual and moral climate of society, its historical roots that feed the social life of generations. The role and significance of patriotism increase at sharp turns in history, when the objective trends in the development of society are accompanied by an increase in the tension of the forces of its citizens (wars, invasions, social conflicts, revolutionary upheavals, aggravation of crises, struggle for power, natural and other disasters, etc.) . The manifestations of patriotism in such periods are marked by high noble impulses, special sacrifice in the name of one's people, one's Motherland, which makes one speak of patriotism as a complex and, of course, an extraordinary phenomenon. In the 40s and 50s of the XIX-th century, in sharp discussions between the Slavophiles (K.S. Aksakov, I.V. Kireevsky, A.S. Khomyakov) and the "Westerners" (T.N. Granovsky, K.D. Kavelin , S.M. Solovyov) arose the concept of the historical development of Russia, in which the Slavophiles persistently pursued the idea that the Russian way of life is unique and inimitable, fundamentally different from the way of Western peoples. In their opinion, since the time of Peter I, who arbitrarily violated the harmonious development of Russia, the state has lost a stable connection with the people, the intelligentsia has broken away from people's life, adopting Western models of lifestyle. Westerners, on the other hand, correlated the concept of "Fatherland" with two substances of the formation of a person's patriotic consciousness - the state and the individual.

They assessed Russian identity as backwardness, glorifying Peter I for the fact that it was under him that the foundations of statehood were laid, the liberation of the individual from the fetters of the tribal system began.

II. METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS

The methodological basis of the study is made up of general theoretical approaches: systemic, activity-based, generalization of pedagogical experience, combinations; both pedagogical and ethno-cultural, philosophical and ethnographic consideration of the phenomenon of Russian patriotism in its local forms of existence. The approach of E.S. Markaryan, who systematizes philosophical, sociological and ethnographic methods. Culturological analysis demanded in methodological terms the unification of ethnographic, philological, aesthetic and psychological approaches. When studying patriotism in an ethnic context, we relied mainly on the dominant domestic methodological tradition, the evolutionary-historical version of the dialectical approach, as well as on the instrumentalist-constructive approach.

Over the past few years, Russian society has made its choice in favor of freedom and democracy. This is evidenced by: a) the deepening of the political and legal unity of the country; b) stabilization of economic growth; c) improving the well-being of citizens, including by investing significant resources in the social sphere aimed at overcoming the demographic crisis (priority national projects in the field of healthcare, education, agriculture, housing construction), which stimulates the expectation of positive changes in society; d) strengthening Russia's international positions, strengthening its sovereignty and influence on world processes. The following guidelines for the policy of the Russian state can be considered promising trends in the development of Russia in the medium term:

- a strong, efficient, democratic, social, rule of law state with an economy that ensures high living standards for every citizen of Russia;
- a free society consolidated on the basis of spiritual and moral values with its historical mission of organic
- synthesis of various poles of world civilization in order to form the humanistic values of the future world order.

Today, patriotism is revealed in a new function: to protect the country not only from visible enemies (as it was in history), but above all from routine, stagnation, liberalism and cosmopolitanism. This protection does not mean creating a barrier in communication with the modern world, but above all the awareness of one's own lagging behind it, the need to eliminate this gap with one's own forces and resources through the consolidation of society, the promotion of ideals and goals that are attractive to society and that can actually be achievable. Patriotism corresponds to the country's desire for modernization, for a sharp increase in the efficiency of the economy, for the concentration of all social forces for a breakthrough, and expresses a strategic position in the life-meaning positions of the individual, in rallying the intentions of the collective, programs for stabilizing society and the political interests of the state. The state of Russian society depends on the quality of fundamental ideas, values and meanings that function in the new historical realities. For patriotic education, this is of particular importance, because it does not tolerate a void that reveals itself in a break in intergenerational continuity, and as a result, the extinction of historical sociocultural continuity. The difference between the semantic attitudes of older and younger has recently become critical and threatens the success of the transfer of sociocultural experience, produces conflicts and alienation. Overcoming contradictions between generations is possible if a general strategy for the development of education is determined and a specific consolidated action plan is developed in the implementation of which all structures of the state, local government and civil society take part. The development of public activity of the population on the basis of its patriotism within the framework of the territorial organization and value being actually determines the formation of the institutional organization of the local community. Usually, the structuring of a local community is understood in terms of a formal administrative-territorial division. However, such an understanding does not reveal the most important thing - the sources of the social energy that determines the desire of the population for social organization, as well as the formation of social self-government mechanisms, which are the basis for the formation of the local community.

Thus, patriotism can be defined as follows: it is the most important mobilization resource of society (social group, ethnic group, individual), aimed at integrating the conditions, forces and means essential for the most important strategic, geopolitical, national, cultural and other problems. Consequently, patriotism is a strategic position that must be developed and clearly defined in the life-meaning priorities of the individual, in rallying the intentions of the collective, in programs for the stabilization of Russian society, in the political interests of the state.

The formation of the self-awareness of future generations must begin from the early period of a person's life in a family, a preschool institution, because this period, according to most researchers (I. S. Kon, V. V. Stolin, L. D. Oleinik, I. V. Dubrovina), is a period of age sensitivity for the formation of this personal education.

The development of patriotic self-awareness in adolescence will contribute to the integrity of his ideas about the image of the Motherland, the historical practice of protecting and building the Fatherland.

The self-awareness of adolescents at this time is directed to the awareness of their own qualities that are important for future activities, the vector of which will be the orientation to serve the Fatherland. Based on the foregoing, older adolescence is considered as the most significant period in the formation of patriotic self-awareness.

The main means of forming patriotic self-consciousness is the actualization of images of service to the Fatherland. Obviously, the process of formation of the patriotic self-consciousness of young generations is of a complex nature, involving the creation of a system of pedagogical conditions universal for Russia, the development of which is the problem of long-term scientific research.

Thus, one of the priority goals of patriotic education at the initial stage of schooling should be the formation of patriotic self-awareness through the mechanisms of self and mutual identification.

The integration of state guidelines and value orientations of teachers, children and parents serves as the basis for concretizing the tasks of educating patriotism among modern students. Civil and patriotic spiritual and moral-volitional qualities are a single complex and are considered in a dialectical relationship.

It is customary to judge a person by the nature of his actions, acts of behavior, results of activity, value bases of relations: a person who is indifferent to the fate of his Fatherland cannot be moral; a moral person cannot but be a defender and builder of the Fatherland. A weak-willed, conforming, dependent, dependent person will be neither active nor spiritual. A.S. Makarenko wrote: "... there can be no hesitation - to strive to educate the brave, honest, persistent or cowardly, cowardly and deceitful: everyone should be brave, courageous, brave, hardworking, patriot."

According to the monitoring of public opinion conducted by the Institute for Socio-Political Research of the Russian Academy of Sciences in 2019-2021, the main patriotic guidelines of the population of the Russian Federation can be represented as follows:

Love for the Motherland - 63%;

Love for one's family, relatives and friends - 50%;

Love for the native city, village, home - 42%;

Love for the native ashes - 8%;

Love for Russian culture - 38%;

Love for the people - 27%.

At present, deep social and economic transformations are being carried out in Russia with the aim of transitioning to a legal democratic state with a market economy.

An important point of modern ideas about the role of patriotism in the regulation of social processes is the distinction between objective and subjective types of regulation, depending on the presence or absence of conscious regulatory actions. The objective impact includes such types of it as natural, socio-cultural and production-economic.

The subjective appears as a conscious impact of the subject on social processes. Objective regulation is carried out spontaneously, independently of consciousness.

To educate future patriots in the face of today's youth, it is necessary to cooperate with educational institutions, families, teachers and the children themselves. Only by helping each other, you can achieve the desired goal - to bring up a true patriot. Students are provided with various opportunities to realize their needs and interests. And today the leading position is occupied by the military-patriotic direction of educating students. On October 29, 2015, the All-Russian military-patriotic social movement "Yunarmia" was created. The Yunarmey movement was created on the initiative of the Russian Ministry of Defense and supported by the President of the Russian Federation. It is designed to unite all organizations and bodies involved in the pre-conscription training of citizens in order to systematize the patriotic movement, as well as to captivate students with military-patriotic topics. The number of participants in the movement, according to July 2017, amounted to about 140,000 people; over the entire period of its existence, the headquarters of the movement were opened in all 85 constituent entities of the Russian Federation. Today, any student from 11 to 18 years old can join the Yunarmiya, because membership in the organization is open and voluntary. The main goal of this movement is to arouse the interest of the younger generation in geography, the history of Russia and its peoples, heroes, outstanding scientists and commanders. Any student, military-patriotic organization, club or search party can join the movement. It is assumed that members of the movement in their free time will be engaged in volunteer activities, take part in cultural and sports events, receive additional education, first aid skills. However, besides this, other types of patriotic educational activities are carried out.

Such transformations as the introduction of the market, new technologies, etc., are only superstructural structures in relation to the original forms of life that exist and existed in Russia and its regions, the problem is that this or that superstructural structure should be provided with an underlying activity at its foundation. It is the unity and harmony of the initial activity and the corresponding idea of the correspondence of the interests of the individual, the collective, society and the state that opens up new sources of creative social energy. This is seen as a path from understanding the imperatives of the future to the formation of real social structures that implement such an understanding.

III. CONCLUSION

Tomorrow in Russia depends on how measured and far-sighted the measures taken today to introduce new standards of quality and accessibility of education will be, while unconditionally preserving the best national traditions, which consist in integrating the phenomenon of patriotism with the realities of modern education and aimed at the social future of the modern generation of young Russian citizens. Traditions are built on the sovereignty of Russia.

The conceptual foundations of patriotic education are designed to play the role of a methodological regulator for federal, municipal bodies, institutions and organizations to develop and implement in their educational space a system for the formation of a person of culture, a citizen and a patriot - a representative of the generation of the 21st century. They are aimed at the search by the subjects of the educational process of a mechanism for improving the formation of a person of culture, a citizen and a patriot, blocking the negative ideological, spiritual and vital influences of society, overcoming social diseases, socialization and adaptation of the individual.

It is the focus on the social demand of young people, the awareness by adolescents and young people of their "need", significance for society, the social order for youth creativity and activity that give a huge positive impetus to the development of the values of patriotism, dramatically increase its effectiveness and impact on the process of learning, self-education and self-improvement.

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ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПАТРИОТИЧЕСКОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ МОЛОДЁЖИ В РОССИИ

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Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются факторы повышения эффективности патриотического воспитания молодёжи, поиск средств и технологий, соизмеримых с этим процессом в России. Показано, что задачей патриотического воспитания сегодня является формирование просвещенного и убежденного патриота-гражданина, обладающего не только чувством любви к Родине, но и знанием ее истории, культуры, причастности к жизни народа. Особое внимание уделяется возрождению утраченных обрядов и праздников, которые могут стать эффективным способом приобщения современной молодёжи к своим культурным корням, основанным на патриотических убеждениях и чувствах, осознании неразрывной связи со своим народом, его традиционным образом жизни.

Ключевые слова: церковь, патриотизм, народ, государство, вера.

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